

1 **Magma interactions, crystal mush formation, timescales, and unrest during caldera**
2 **collapse and lateral eruption at ocean island basaltic volcanoes (Piton de la Fournaise, La**
3 **Réunion)**

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12 **Keywords**

13 Olivine; caldera; melt inclusion; diffusion; timescales; crystal mush

14 **ABSTRACT**

15 The dynamics of magmatic processes at large mafic ocean island volcanoes control
16 the likely locations (central caldera versus flanks) and timing of their eruptions. Crystals
17 and their melt inclusions are key witnesses of these processes but are rarely studied in
18 detail and in the same samples. Here we report the crystal and melt inclusion
19 compositions of the April 2007 caldera-forming eruption of Piton de la Fournaise volcano

20 and discuss how they relate to geophysical unrest monitoring data. Olivine crystals show
21 mainly normal zoning (decrease in Mg/Fe) towards the rims, and also around some melt
22 inclusions. Many crystals also show fine-scale skeletal structures defined by high
23 phosphorus concentrations. Melt inclusions contain 53-205 ppm CO₂ and 0.25-1.1 wt%
24 H₂O, and δD (δD values expressed as δD_{VSMOW}) ranges from -135 to 62 ‰. Monitoring data
25 show that inflation of the edifice started about a month before the first 2007 eruption:
26 magma intrusion occurred at ≈ 3 km below sea level, and quickly migrated towards
27 shallower depths (about 1 km above sea level). Such a time frame of magma movement is
28 recorded in the chemical zoning of the olivine crystals that massively and quickly
29 crystallized when reaching shallow depth, without significant interactions between
30 resident and intruding magmas. The intrusion was followed by lateral flank eruption and
31 caldera collapse. The chemical zoning of the olivine crystal rims and around the melt
32 inclusions indicates that the newly created crystal-mush moved laterally towards the
33 surface in matter of days to 3 months. Post-caldera samples show significant H⁺ loss, likely
34 due to the depressurization of the magmatic system stored at shallow level. Our findings
35 are different from other mafic ocean island volcanoes or stratovolcanoes (e.g. Kilauea,
36 Canary Islands, and Etna), where crystals commonly record magma mixing between
37 evolved and shallow melts and intruding mafic melts. We speculate that the difference
38 between our findings and those of similar mafic ocean island volcanoes is due to the
39 variety of magma supply rates from depth.

40

41 **1. Introduction**

42 Understanding the processes that occur in the magma plumbing system below ocean
43 island volcanoes and how they relate to monitoring data, are key current topics of
44 research because they can lead to improved volcanic hazard assessment (e.g., Cashman et
45 al., 2017). Crystal compositions and melt inclusions are direct sources of information on
46 the architecture and dynamics of the plumbing system. Crystal zoning patterns can inform
47 us of the range of magmatic environments, and of the likely processes that lead to
48 eruption (e.g. Albert et al., 2015; Kahl et al., 2011). In the last couple of decades many
49 studies have quantified the timescales of pre-eruptive magmatic processes via
50 combination of diffusion and crystal growth models, in particular using olivine (e.g. Costa
51 et al., 2008; Costa and Dungan, 2005; Shea et al., 2015; Pankhurst et al., 2018). A
52 complementary view of the plumbing system is provided by detailed studies of melt
53 inclusions. The variability of major, trace, and volatile element concentrations of the
54 inclusions also informs us of the heterogeneity and architecture of the system (e.g.
55 Danyushevsky et al., 2004; Métrich et al., 2009; Rasmussen et al., 2018), although the
56 major and volatile element record of melt inclusions can be modified by post-entrapment
57 processes (e.g. Lloyd et al., 2013; Danyushevsky et al., 2000). For rapidly quenched
58 samples, the volatile concentrations (H₂O and CO₂) coupled with experimentally calibrated
59 solubility models allows the determination of the volatile saturation pressure, which can
60 be translated into minimum depth of magma storage (Collins et al., 2009; Frezzotti, 2001).
61 Despite the complementary information provided by crystal zoning and the melt
62 inclusions studies, these have rarely been studied together (e.g. Rasmussen et al., 2018;
63 Ruth et al., 2018), and thus we are losing opportunities to obtain a more comprehensive

64 view of the system. Coupling of the depth of magma storage with the times of magma
65 movement allows us to propose links with the eruptive behavior and different phases of
66 eruptions, and especially with the monitoring data describing the unrest preceding the
67 eruptions (Albert et al., 2016, 2015, Kahl et al., 2011; Pankhurst et al., 2018).

68 The complex dynamics between the central caldera, lateral magma transport, and
69 eruption sites of the April 2018 activity at Kilauea volcano exemplify the need to better
70 understand the plumbing system and the tectonic control of volcanic activity at ocean
71 island volcanoes. Here we investigate the magmatic processes associated with caldera
72 collapse and lateral magma transport recorded in olivine crystals and their melt inclusions
73 on selected samples from the largest historical eruption of Piton de la Fournaise (Michon
74 et al., 2007).

75

76 **2. Background**

77 **2.1. Geological setting**

78 Piton de la Fournaise (PdF) is one of the most active intra-plate basaltic shield volcanoes
79 on Earth (1 eruption every 9 months on average since 1930; Peltier et al., 2009). Collapse
80 of the summit caldera is a rare event, but it occurred in April 2007 during one of its largest
81 eruptions ($\approx 0.15 \text{ km}^3$ of Dense Rock Equivalent; DRE) that lasted 31 days, and led to a ca. 1
82 km wide x 0.34 km deep depression due to the summit caldera floor collapse (e.g.
83 Staudacher et al., 2009).

84 The 2007 eruptions started on the summit of the volcano on February 18th (Fig. 1a). A
85 second small eruption followed on the upper SE flank on March 30th, and from April 2nd
86 until May 1st the eruption moved to lower elevations. The eruption that occurred at low
87 altitude between April and May was the main phase in duration and volume. Previous
88 studies have shown that the bulk-rock composition and crystal content of the erupted
89 magmas changed with time (Di Muro et al., 2014). Aphyric basalt erupted in February and
90 cotectic basalt in March have relatively high Sr isotope ratio ($^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr} = 0.70420\text{-}0.70418$).
91 Aphyric magmas were also erupted at the beginning of April event, but the crystal content
92 increased rapidly before caldera collapse (olivine basalt) and remained high
93 (oceanite/olivine-rich basalts) after the collapse event until the end of the eruption (more
94 details about crystallinity can be found in Di Muro et al., 2014). The increase in crystal
95 content coincided with a decrease in Sr isotope values ($^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr} = 0.70412\text{-}0.70418$), with
96 the lowest value measured in a lava erupted just before the summit collapse on April 5th.
97 The evolution in the petrological, chemical and isotopic features of the 2007 lavas and
98 tephra has been attributed to eruption of magmas stored in multiple independent and
99 shallow pockets which were pressurized by a deep input (Di Muro et al., 2014).

100

101 **2.2. Monitoring data preceding and during the 2007 eruptions**

102 The OVPF (Observatoire Volcanologique du Piton de la Fournaise) has monitored the PdF
103 volcano since 1980, and the 2007 eruption was recorded on a range of monitoring
104 networks, including seismic and geodetic. Long-term precursors of the 2007 eruptions

105 were identified in tilt-signal from a distal station (RER) located on the northern flank of the
106 volcano that showed an inflation-deflation cycle that started on January 2007 and lasted
107 until the end of the eruption in May (Fontaine et al., 2014). This period of inflation has
108 been attributed to a single deep injection of magma (source at ca. 3 km depth below sea
109 level, b.s.l.; Fontaine et al., 2014). Pressurization of the shallow part of the plumbing
110 system following a deep intrusion has also been recently observed in PdF during the 2014-
111 2015 unrest (Peltier et al., 2016).

112 **3. Samples and Methods**

113 **3.1. Samples description**

114 We use the same samples studied by Di Muro et al (2014). These include the pre-
115 caldera olivine-basalts (CM labels) erupted between April 2nd and 4th, and post-caldera
116 crystal-rich oceanites (251 labels) emitted near the end of the eruption on April 25th.
117 Oceanites contain up to 60 wt% of olivine phenocrysts ranging from mm to several cm; we
118 have focused on crystals < 2 mm. We measured the chemical zoning patterns of a subset
119 of olivine crystals, which were previously studied for their melt inclusion composition and
120 volatile contents (Di Muro et al., 2014). We also report new isotopic analyses of H (values
121 expressed as δD_{VSMOW}) for some of these inclusions. Our new dataset includes the zoning
122 patterns of 13 and 14 olivine crystals from the CM- and 251-samples, respectively, and the
123 δD measurement in 25 melt inclusions.

124 The pre-caldera samples are cm-size scoria clasts erupted during the initial intense
125 fountaining activity and that should have experienced rapid quenching in air. Post-caldera

126 lava samples (ca. 10 cm large blobs) were taken close to the vent and were quenched in a
127 bucket of water to minimize post-eruptive modifications.

128

129 **3.2. Analytical methods**

130 We have used standard procedures for the data acquisition and modelling that we
131 summarize below. Further details can be found in the Supplementary Material. The
132 quantitative analyses and the X-ray elemental distribution maps of olivine were obtained
133 using a JEOL JXA 8530F field emission Electron Probe MicroAnalyzer (EPMA). The
134 crystallographic axes were determined by Electron Backscattered Diffraction (EBSD) using
135 a JEOL JSM-7600F equipped with an Oxford/HKL detector and HKL CHANNEL5 software
136 (both at Nanyang Technological University, Singapore). The analytical conditions are
137 detailed in the Supplementary Material and are the same as in Albert et al. (2015).

138 Major, trace, and volatile (H_2O , CO_2 , S and Cl) element concentrations in melt
139 inclusions have been published in Di Muro et al. (2014). Water was analyzed by Raman
140 spectroscopy with an argon ion laser, a Labram HR800 spectrometer (ENS-Lyon), and an
141 Olympus microscope. Carbon concentrations and hydrogen isotopic compositions were
142 analyzed using the Cameca IMS1270 ion microprobe at CRPG-CNRS-Nancy. The D/H ratios
143 were determined by measuring the OD^-/OH^- ratios, in monocollection mode with a mass
144 resolution of 15 000 to get a complete separation of $^{16}\text{OH}_2^-$ and $^{16}\text{OD}^-$. The hydrogen
145 isotopic compositions of the melt inclusions were acquired following the procedure of
146 Métrich and Deloule (2014) and detailed in the Supplementary Material.

147

148 **3.3. Modelling**

149 **3.3.1. Mg-Fe, Ca, Ni and P diffusion in olivine**

150 Twenty-three rim-to-core, and eight melt inclusion-to-crystal boundary concentration
151 profiles in olivine were obtained for Si, Fe, Mg, Ca, Ni and P (depending on the crystal). We
152 modelled the Fe–Mg, Ni and Ca concentration gradients using the program DIPRA (Girona
153 and Costa, 2013). We apply the anisotropy correction to the results according to equation
154 #5 of Costa and Chakraborty (2004). We report the uncertainty on diffusion times that
155 accounts for analytical and temperature uncertainty as calculated by DIPRA. In addition,
156 DIPRA also calculates a parameter called “discrepancy”, which is basically a goodness of
157 the fit (Girona and Costa, 2013) and which is reported in Table 1. Most of our diffusion
158 times were obtained from fits with a discrepancy of $\leq 10\%$. The temperature and oxygen
159 fugacity (fO_2) used for modelling are $1200\pm 10^\circ\text{C}$ and 1.2 log units below the NNO buffer
160 for the reverse zoning profiles (pre-caldera samples; labels CM), and $1160\pm 10^\circ\text{C}$ and 0.8
161 log units below the NNO buffer for the normal zoning profiles (pre- and post-caldera
162 samples; labels CM and 251). Temperatures have been calculated with the Fo values and
163 the melt inclusions composition by using the olivine-melt equilibrium geothermometer of
164 Helz and Thornber (1987), as described by Di Muro et al. (2014). Oxygen fugacity has been
165 calculated according to Kress and Carmichael (1991). For initial and boundary conditions
166 we used the same as those in Albert et al. (2015) which are detailed in the Supplementary
167 Material. We have also performed a 2-dimensional diffusion model with a finite
168 differences code for one melt inclusion that correlates the anisotropy effect on the

169 chemical diffusion and the data acquired with the X-ray distribution maps. Finally, we
170 have modelled one P compositional profile in the olivine leading up to the olivine-melt
171 inclusion interface. The P traverse has been modelled separately with an initial step-like
172 profile as required by the S-shaped compositional profile.

173

174 **3.4. H⁺ diffusion**

175 The H₂O content of the melt inclusions may vary due to post-entrapment diffusion of
176 H⁺ through the host olivine or/and due to degassing (Lloyd et al., 2013; Bucholz et al.,
177 2013; Chen et al., 2011; Gaetani et al., 2012). Thus, it is critical to determine the extent to
178 which melt inclusion data record a variation of entrapment depths versus the partial re-
179 equilibration via dehydration during magma ascent or cooling on the earth's surface. Here
180 we make use of the H₂O and δD values and attempt to establish the roles of each process.

181 We have modelled the diffusive re-equilibration of H₂O of eight melt inclusions using
182 the method of Qin et al. (1992), which considers a spherical melt inclusion of radius *a*
183 hosted in a spherical crystal of radius *b*, and we report the details of the parameter values
184 and equations used in the calculation in Supplementary Material. Following Di Muro et al.
185 (2014), we have assumed that the largest measured concentrations have not been
186 modified via diffusion and thus we have used them as initial values (e.g. 1-1.3 wt % H₂O).
187 We discuss the validity of this assumption in Section 4.4. We have modelled the water loss
188 via H⁺ diffusion to test whether the D/H ratios (δD) versus H₂O content in our samples
189 from the pre- and post-caldera eruptions can be explained by a dehydration process. We

190 have considered an average melt inclusion with a radius of 50 μm hosted in an average
191 spherical crystal with a radius of 500 μm , a temperature of 1160°C, an initial concentration
192 of H_2O that varies from 1 to 1.3 wt %, and an initial $\delta\text{D} = -100 \text{‰}$.

193

194 **3.5. H_2O degassing**

195 In addition to H^+ diffusive re-equilibration, both the water content and the hydrogen
196 isotopic signature of the melt can also be affected by melt degassing. We have addressed
197 this by modelling the variations of δD under closed (equation #1) and open-system
198 (equation #2) conditions (Taylor, 1986):

$$199 \quad \delta D_{melt} = \delta D_i - (1 - F) 1000 \ln \alpha \quad (1)$$

$$200 \quad \delta D_{melt} = \delta D_i - (1000 + \delta D_i)(1 - F^{\alpha-1}) \quad (2)$$

201 where δD_i is the initial composition of the melt, and F is the fraction of water remaining
202 dissolved in the melt. We have calculated the fractionation factor α according to De Hoog
203 et al. (2009). As initial magma composition we have considered the sample
204 REU091110_DM-CM15 from Di Muro et al. (2014).

205

206 **4. Results**

207 **4.1. Zoning patterns of olivine crystals**

208 Olivine crystals from the early tephra emitted before caldera collapse (CM-samples)
209 and from the post-caldera collapse lava (251-samples) display similar compositions and
210 zoning patterns (Fig. 1; and Supplementary Material Fig. 1), with Fo [Fo = 100 x
211 Mg/(Mg+Fe)] values ranging from about 82 to about 86 (Table 1). BSE (Back-scattered
212 Electron) images, X-Ray compositional maps, and EPMA traverses of phenocrysts show a
213 slight reverse zoning (increase of about 1 mol % Fo) in the central part of crystals, with
214 plateaus at Fo \approx 84-85 and at Fo \approx 85-86, followed by normal zoning towards the rim (Fo \approx 82-
215 83; Fig. 1). Olivine in the vicinity of melt inclusions may show a compositional halo that is
216 normally zoned towards the melt inclusion, with similar Fo to that of the crystal rims (Fig.
217 1c, f and g). Ni follows the zoning patterns of Fo, whereas Ca is typically a mirror image of
218 Fo (Fig. 2a). The 2D Fe-Mg compositional maps around melt inclusions show zoning (Fig.
219 2d and f) that is in accord with the Fe-Mg diffusion anisotropy (see also below). 2D X-Ray
220 maps of phosphorous (Fig. 1d and h) show complex zoning patterns which have been
221 interpreted as an early episode of fast skeletal growth (Welsch et al., 2014) that lead to
222 trapping of the melt inclusions (e.g. Manzini et al., 2017; Ruth et al., 2018). We measured
223 a few profiles across the P-rich bands (e.g. Fig. 1h and 2g), which are S-shaped and have
224 concentrations between about 0.01 and < 0.005 mol% P. It is worth noting that crystal
225 rims and compositional haloes around melt inclusion record only normal Fo zoning, and
226 that the zoning patterns did not change during the eruption despite the changes in
227 crystallinity. This suggests that the crystals are simply recording magma transport towards
228 the surface (mainly lateral) rather than magma mixing or open system behavior in the
229 magma plumbing system. Modelling the interface between the olivine and the melt

230 inclusion is an independent test for retrieving the thermal history of the crystals. The
231 similarity of the crystal rim and the melt inclusion-haloes zoning patterns is key to support
232 the magma transport hypothesis versus magma mixing, and therefore we have also
233 modelled these diffusion profiles.

234

235 **4.2. Timescales recorded by olivine crystals and melt inclusions**

236 Representative crystals were selected for modelling the concentration profiles and to
237 calculate the timescales according to chemical diffusion. This includes crystals with
238 reverse zoning at the core and normal zoning at the rims and towards the melt inclusions
239 (Fig. 2). Diffusion modelling of reversely zoned Fo in the central part of the crystals yields
240 good fits with low discrepancy values (Fig. 2a) and relatively long times of two to three
241 years. However, the Ca and Ni fits generally have discrepancies close to 20% (Fig. 2a),
242 which indicates that their shapes are not well explained by simple diffusion (Table 1).
243 Moreover, visual inspection of the compositional gradients for Fo, Ni, Ca shows that they
244 are all of about the same length, which should not be the case if diffusion was the only
245 controlling factor given that they have different diffusivities. These observations make us
246 think that a significant part of the reverse zoning profile could be due to growth, and thus
247 that our times are overestimates of the real time. We also note that the reverse Fo zoning
248 involves less than 1 mol% and thus could be explained by relatively small changes of melt
249 composition, temperature or oxygen fugacity rather than mixing of different magmas
250 from different storage regions (e.g. Pankhurst et al., 2018).

251 Modelling of Fo, Ni and Ca zoning towards the crystal rims, and near the melt inclusion
252 margins, give a consistent answer (Fig. 2), with low discrepancy values and times ranging
253 from about 3 to 157 days (Fig. 3), although the majority of times (82 %) are less than two
254 months (Table 1). Olivine crystals from the late-erupted lava give timescales slightly
255 shorter than the pre-caldera samples (Table 1). Normal zoning of the Fo concentration
256 towards the interface between the olivine and the melt inclusion for the pre- and post-
257 caldera samples (including the 2D model) (Fig. 2; Supplementary Materials Fig.2) give
258 timescales of about 2 to 30 days (Table 1), and overlap with those of the crystal rims.

259 The normal zoning towards the rim and around melt inclusions could be due to a drop
260 in temperature and/or water content while in transport towards the surface. For example,
261 MELTS (Ghiorso and Sack, 1995) simulations show that a decrease of 10-15°C decreases 1
262 mol% Fo. Moreover, since the timescales calculated for the pre- and post-caldera olivine
263 are similar, the process leading to the generation of the normal zoning in the olivine
264 crystals is unlikely to be due to a pre-eruptive process in the reservoir. In that case, the
265 late erupted post-caldera crystals should record about a month longer residence time. Our
266 timescales support the hypothesis that the zoning is the result of the lateral transport
267 from the mush zone to the vent in response to the change of environmental conditions.

268 We have also modelled one P profile (Figs. 1 and 2) at the interface between the
269 olivine and a melt inclusion, and this yields a time of almost two years (Table 1). However,
270 it is unclear if the full profile is due solely to diffusion. The halo of low P concentration
271 around the melt inclusion (Fig. 1h) could reflect a more complex process of dissolution
272 and crystallization (Manzini et al., 2017; Schiano et al., 2006) and might be revealing the

273 extent of post-entrapment crystallization. Therefore, the times obtained from P are likely
274 to be a maximum.

275

276 **4.3. Volatile contents and δD of melt inclusions**

277 The H₂O and CO₂ contents of the melt inclusions (Table 2) range from 0.6-1.1 wt% and
278 53 to 125 ppm, respectively, for the pre-caldera tephra, and from 0.32-0.82 wt % and 56
279 to 205 ppm for the post-caldera lava (Di Muro et al., 2014). These concentrations
280 correspond to low saturation pressures (<0.5-0.4 kbar; Table 2; Fig. 4). The melt inclusions
281 from the pre-caldera samples yield, on average, higher volatile saturation pressure, with
282 respect to most post-caldera melt inclusions. Di Muro et al. (2014) calculated an average
283 saturation pressure of 270 bar for the 2007 eruption using the Newman and Lowenstern
284 (2002) model, slightly higher than the new average (250 bar) estimated using the Papale
285 et al. (2006) model. As already shown by Di Muro et al. (2016), the two models provide
286 very similar results in the pressure range < 1 kbar typically recorded by melt inclusions in
287 Pdf oceanites. Average pressure calculated using both models corresponds to a lithostatic
288 depth range of 1280-1100 m below the volcano summit (ca. 1.5 km above sea level)
289 considering a linear density increase from 1600 to 3400 kg m⁻³ (Di Muro et al., 2014). The
290 maximum pressure recorded by the 2007 melt inclusion dataset is consistent with magma
291 storage slightly above the sea level, but most melt inclusions record lower
292 pressure/trapping depth. Pre- and post-caldera melt inclusions have distinct temperature
293 ranges. Temperatures calculated for post-entrapment crystallization show a larger range

294 (1145 to 1232°C) in pre-caldera samples, compared to post-caldera melt inclusions (1178
295 to 1199°C; Fig. 4b). Di Muro et al. (2014) stress that the high-temperature range (>1200°C)
296 is inconsistent with the low average Fo content in olivine and the relatively evolved
297 composition of aphyric lavas and glassy matrix melts. The lowest average temperature is
298 recorded by melt inclusions in the early erupted cotectic basalts of March 2007 (1186-
299 1134 °C). These more evolved and cooler melts are also more degassed. A marked drop in
300 dissolved water content (0.3 wt % < H₂O < 0.5 wt %) at constant temperature is recorded
301 in some melt inclusions of the post caldera phase. On the contrary, melt inclusions of the
302 pre-caldera phase having experienced marked post-entrapment modification do not show
303 significant water loss.

304 The δD of melt inclusions varies from -135 to -10.3 ‰ and -77 to 62 ‰, for the pre- and
305 post-caldera samples, respectively (Table 2). The pre-caldera melt inclusions display only a
306 slight decrease in δD with the decrease of water (with the exception of three melt
307 inclusions). In contrast, the post-caldera melt inclusions show a general increase in the
308 D/H ratios when the H₂O concentration decreases (Fig. 5). We stress here that melt
309 inclusions having experienced marked water depletion (H₂O<0.5 wt%) have not been
310 analyzed for their D/H composition. To explain the variation in H₂O content, δD and CO₂
311 we have considered two possible end-member scenarios (see section 5.2).

312

313 **4.4. Timescales of H₂O loss via diffusion**

314 We have calculated the H₂O diffusive re-equilibration timescales for a wide range of
315 parameter values and sizes. Although the re-equilibration degree varies significantly,
316 (between 10 and 70 %; Table 3), independently of the size or distance to the crystal rim of
317 each melt inclusion, the timescales between different melt inclusions are similar. This
318 suggests that our assumptions about treating all melt inclusions with a similar initial and
319 equilibrium values are likely to be appropriated. The timescales calculated with diffusion
320 parallel [001] are of a few hours, and those parallel to [100] and [010] are between one
321 and six days (Supplementary Material Fig. 3). The only exception is the 251-20a melt
322 inclusion, with a radius around three times bigger than the rest and connected by a
323 fracture (Supplementary Material Fig. 1b and c).

324

325 **5. Discussion**

326

327 **5.1. Magmatic processes recorded by the olivine crystals and their melt inclusions**

328 Our results support the existence of different magma pockets below the PdF
329 summit. The occurrence of a multilevel magma storage system is consistent with the
330 presence of various seismic low-velocity zones below the cone of PdF (e.g. Prôno et al.,
331 2009). Magmas erupted in February, March, and April 2007 have distinct Sr isotopic
332 signatures. Olivine and melt inclusion compositions of March cotectic basalt are consistent
333 with the eruption of a small volume of relatively evolved melt with a temperature of ca.
334 1160°C. (Fig. 4b; Di Muro et al., 2014). The sudden and rapid isotopic shift recorded in

335 lavas emitted at the beginning of caldera collapse (lowest value in $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$) has been
336 interpreted by Di Muro et al. (2014) as the evidence of the new magmatic input that
337 pressurized and led to eruption of melts located in the shallow (< 0.5 kbar) plumbing
338 system. The crystal-rich lavas erupted after April 5th contain olivine with variable isotopic
339 compositions (see Di Muro et al., 2014). However, we stress that isotopic data have been
340 acquired on a large range of crystal sizes (from cm to mm), while crystal zoning and melt
341 inclusion data discussed here concern the crystal size population < 2 mm.

342 The relatively low Fo values of the olivine (86 to 82) from both, pre- and post-
343 caldera eruptions, the absence of reverse Fo zoning near the rims, and the rarity of MgO-
344 rich glass do not support a scenario of pre-eruptive mixing between a primitive deep
345 magma and a shallow evolved one, as has been reported at other ocean island volcanoes
346 (e.g. Albert et al., 2016). Another possibility is that the intruding melts were relatively
347 evolved (MgO < 8 wt%) and interacted with a more mafic crystal pile left over from
348 previous eruptions. However, several observations make this possibility quite unlikely: (1)
349 the Fo values and extent of zoning of the crystal rims and between melt inclusions and
350 crystal interface are the same, (2) we do not find any crystals with evolved cores of similar
351 compositions to the rims, and (3) the time scales obtained from P modeling show that the
352 crystal cores could not have remained at magmatic temperatures for more than about 1.5
353 years. These observations are more consistent with the Fo zoning due to magma transport
354 towards the surface rather than the classical view of mixing between a mafic melt and an
355 evolved cumulate. The low volatile saturation pressures calculated from the melt
356 inclusions indicate that the erupted magmas were stored at quite shallow depths (ca. 0.5

357 km a.s.l.). The combined observations of chemical zoning, timescales, and shallow
358 entrapment depths of melt inclusions can be interpreted as intrusion of magma at shallow
359 depth that grew Fo84-86 crystals which would be in equilibrium with more magnesian
360 melts than those erupted. Thus many of the olivine crystals in fact grew and trapped the
361 melt inclusions during the time period since the beginning of unrest and the end of the
362 eruption (e.g. about 3 months). The normal zoning towards the crystal rims and around
363 the melt inclusions (e.g., Fo82-83) is likely due to transport of the magma from the
364 shallow reservoir located near sea level towards the surface. The lateral transport under
365 Piton de la Fournaise have an associated change in depth of about 1.5 km, and this will
366 generate a change in the magma intensive conditions (e.g. temperature and water loss).
367 Such short times for creating olivine mushes are also consistent with the evidence of fast
368 growth provided by the fine P skeletal zoning (Welsch et al., 2014; this paper). However,
369 given the limited size of our dataset we cannot fully discard the possibility that cumulates
370 contain some crystals recycled from previous events, as suggested by the Sr isotopic
371 differences between the olivine separates and the bulk-rock. These older cumulates are
372 likely represented in the crystal populations larger than those examined in this study.

373

374 **5.2. Entrapment of melt inclusions, degassing and depressurization of the system**

375 The melt inclusions from the pre- and post-caldera samples display two different
376 trends of water content vs. δD (Fig. 5). We have considered two end-member scenarios
377 for the interpretation of these variations. For both cases we first assume that the post-

378 eruptive diffusive modification has not played a major role (e.g. Lloyd et al., 2013). This
379 assumption is appropriated since we did not analyzed inclusions with very low (< 0.45
380 wt%) water content.

381 One end-member scenario is that the melt inclusions are trapped at different depths
382 during magma ascent without diffusive re-equilibration, and the variations of water and
383 δD follow as closed system evolution. This possibility has been considered before to
384 explain the trend of samples from Koolau basalts from Hawaii (Hauri, 2002). Degassing will
385 generate lower values of δD with decreasing water content (e.g. Bouvier et al., 2010), and
386 the pre-caldera melt inclusions follow the degassing trends that we have calculated (Fig.
387 5). The CO_2 and S variation recorded in the melt inclusions also suggests a degassing trend
388 (for further details see Di Muro et al., 2014).

389 The other end-member scenario is that the H_2O and δD variation is due to diffusive
390 loss H^+ from melt inclusions that were trapped at the same depth, e.g. limited role for
391 magma degassing. During magma ascent the melt inclusions would have experienced a
392 progressive diffusive re-equilibration with the external surrounding and more degassed
393 melt. The general increase in δD with the decrease of H_2O in the post-caldera samples
394 suggests diffusive re-equilibration between the melt inclusions and the external melt
395 through the olivine. In this case, the variation in the melt inclusions H_2O content and δD is
396 related to the re-equilibration degree, which depends on the melt inclusion size and
397 position inside the crystal. We have modelled the changes in the δD during dehydration
398 from the initial conditions (Fig. 5). Once the H_2O re-equilibration degree (ϕ) of each melt
399 inclusion has been estimated, the corresponding times can be calculated (see section 3.4).

400 Most of the H₂O and δD values of the pre-caldera melt inclusions fall into a magma
401 degassing trend, whereas those of the post-caldera samples agree with a H⁺ diffusion loss
402 scenario (Fig. 5). If our initial water and δD are not correct, and were instead 1.5-2 wt%
403 and to -150 to -200 ‰, respectively, we could fit all samples with a single diffusive re-
404 equilibration trend. Such low initial δD are unlikely because there is no evidence of crust
405 recycling or dehydrated mantle in the PdF mantle source (Valer et al., 2017). Moreover,
406 maximum dissolved water content documented in PdF magmas is rarely > 1.3 wt% (Di
407 Muro et al., 2016). Another possibility is that the melt inclusions have experienced post-
408 eruptive H⁺ diffusion either during lava emplacement or after water quenching (e.g. Lloyd
409 et al., 2013). This population is most likely represented by melt inclusions with a very low
410 water content (< 0.5 wt%), close to that of the matrix (0.3-0.2 wt%) and recording a very
411 low apparent trapping pressure (P < 150 bar) (see supplementary material). Finally,
412 depressurization of the magma pockets due to the caldera collapse and the sliding of the
413 volcano flank could have promoted H⁺ diffusive re-equilibration at depth before magma
414 movement towards the surface started. The occurrence of two different trends (degassing
415 and H⁺ diffusion) is consistent with the results of Di Muro et al., (2014) who suggested that
416 some of the melt inclusions experienced water loss based on the H₂O-S correlation. We do
417 not find any correlation between the K₂O, CO₂ and H₂O content of the melt inclusions and
418 therefore we have excluded the possibility of CO₂ fluxing (Métrich and Wallace, 2008;
419 Supplementary Material Fig. 4). In conclusion, we suggest that lower pressures calculated
420 for most (except for one melt inclusion) post-caldera melt inclusions with respect to pre-
421 caldera samples result from post-entrapment partial H⁺ loss.

422 The timescales calculated from the H⁺ diffusive re-equilibration are very short
423 compared with the Mg/Fe, Ni and Ca timescales. We interpret these timescales as records
424 of the magma depressurization due to the flank sliding and the caldera collapse rather
425 than magma movement towards the surface. This would explain why the H⁺ diffusive re-
426 equilibration is mainly recorded by the post-caldera melt inclusions, even if some pre-
427 caldera melt inclusions may be also recording the depressurization generated by flank
428 sliding. According to Di Muro et al. (2014) the collapse of a 340 m deep caldera
429 corresponds to a ca. 10 MPa depressurization. This value is consistent with the difference
430 between the pressures calculated for the pre- and post-caldera melt inclusions and gives
431 additional support to our interpretation that the lower H⁺ values of post-caldera samples
432 may reflect fast re-equilibration due to unloading and caldera collapse (Fig. 4). However,
433 given that the post-caldera samples are lavas, we can't fully discard the possibility that
434 water and δD for these samples has been partially affected by degassing on the Earth's
435 surface.

436

437 **5.3. Integration of petrological with monitoring data and sequence of events** 438 **preceding and during the 2007 eruption**

439 The timescales of magma transfer, H⁺ loss, and magma storage depth that we have
440 found can be used to better understand the monitoring data associated with this eruption
441 (e.g. Albert et al., 2016, 2015; Kahl et al., 2011; Rasmussen et al., 2018; Saunders et al.,
442 2012). For the interpretation we have considered together the chemical zoning in olivine

443 crystals, the diffusion modelling timescales, the geochemical data (whole rock
444 compositions) and the geodetical data (Fig. 6).

445 Combination of the monitoring and petrologic data suggests that the new input of
446 magma responsible of the edifice inflation (Fontaine et al., 2014) was located at 3 km
447 b.s.l., but, intruded the shallow magmatic system and triggered the eruption of two
448 shallow magma pockets (the February and March events) but did not interact with them,
449 given their different Sr isotopic compositions. The lavas of these early eruptions are either
450 aphyric (February) or contain rare iron-rich olivine (Fo 81-82; March) (Di Muro et al., 2014;
451 2016). This was followed by extensive and fast crystallization of olivine (Fo 82-86) and the
452 lateral propagation of a sill from a crystal mush (April eruption). According to Froger et al.
453 (2015), the crystal-rich magma would have encountered a pre-existing structural
454 discontinuity, probably compensating for the lack of buoyancy due to the high crystal
455 cargo and triggering a lateral eruption, in contrast with the mainly aphyric basalts from
456 the early summit eruptions. Interestingly, caldera collapse was preceded by the increase
457 in the lava crystal content, suggesting that displacement of the crystal mush contributed
458 to volume changes leading to caldera foundering (Di Muro et al., 2014).

459 The sequence of processes preceding and during the 2007 eruption obtained from
460 combining monitoring, crystal, and melt inclusion information can be explained with the
461 following stages (please see Figs. 6 and 7): (1) In January, inflation started due to new
462 magma intrusion at depth (ca. 3 km b.s.l.) followed by magma movement to the shallow
463 plumbing system (ca. 0.5 km a.s.l.), pressurizing pre-existing magma pockets that moved
464 towards the surface in January. This is consistent with a progressive increase in shallow

465 microseismicity below the volcano summit in January and early February (OVPF
466 unpublished data). This early magma movement is recorded in the crystal timescales
467 (normal zoning; Fig 6c). (2) In February aphyric basalts with high $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ were erupted.
468 Pressurization continued, and olivine records that the pre-caldera magma kept moving
469 towards the surface. (3) March is a period of non-inflation culminating with a sudden flank
470 sliding, and it might correspond to continuous lateral transport of a newly created crystal
471 mush in response to the underlying pressurization. (4) At the end of March, the second
472 eruption took place. The cotectic basalts are evolved and have isotopic compositions
473 different to the February eruption, which suggest they are derived from a different
474 magma pocket (Di Muro et al., 2014). The lateral transport from the crystal mush
475 continues. (5) On April 2nd the distal main eruptive phase starts with the emission of
476 aphyric basalts, and on April 3th the pre-caldera collapse olivine basalts (CM samples)
477 erupt. The water and δD values of melt inclusions mainly record magma degassing (Fig 5)
478 over a shallow pressure range. The timescales of olivine crystals indicate that the magmas
479 that yield the post-caldera eruption already started to move towards the surface (Fig 6d).
480 Two days later, on April 5th the caldera started to collapse. (6) During April the olivine
481 crystals record timescales that suggest magma kept moving after the collapse. Our post-
482 caldera collapse samples (oceanites; 251 samples) were erupted on April 25th. The melt
483 inclusions hosted by the olivine crystals mainly record H^+ loss via diffusion due to the
484 depressurization related to caldera collapse and flank sliding (Fig. 5) or degassing on the
485 Earth's surface due to slow quenching of the samples.

486

487 **6. A role for the magma flux in the architecture of volcanic plumbing systems?**

488 Piton de la Fournaise and Kilauea are intraplate basaltic volcanoes associated with a
489 mantle plume of high activity, and both volcanoes have well-developed shallow magma
490 ponding zones (e.g. Prôno et al., 2009; Sides et al., 2014). However, in contrast with our
491 findings at PdF, magmas erupted from Kilauea during inflation periods reflect mixing
492 between the new input and the shallow reservoir (Lynn et al., 2017; Poland et al., 2012;
493 Sides et al., 2014). Studies of Mt. Etna olivine crystals also show evidence of multiple
494 mixing episodes preceding the eruption (e.g. Kahl et al., 2011), which may reflect a
495 plumbing system made of multiple but well-connected reservoirs due to the high magma
496 flux at this volcano (Kahl et al., 2011). Mafic ocean island volcanoes with lower magma
497 supply rates as the Canary Islands (e.g. Tenerife, El Hierro and La Palma) also display
498 evidence of magma mixing recorded in olivine (e.g. Albert et al., 2015; Klügel et al., 2005).
499 During the El Hierro 2011 eruption, the geophysical monitoring data indicated similar
500 depths to those calculated by geochemical methods, and also evidence for mixing
501 between a shallow evolved melt and a deeper more primitive melt recorded in the olivine
502 crystals (Longpré et al., 2014; López et al., 2012).

503 The different behavior of these systems may be related to their different magma
504 supply rate (e.g. White et al., 2006) and plumbing system architecture. At one end of the
505 spectrum we have the case of high magma flux systems such as Kilauea and Etna, with a
506 plumbing system characterized by open paths and well-connected reservoirs facilitating
507 the interaction between any new intruding melts and those that resided in various
508 pockets. At the other end, we have much less active systems like the Canary Islands where

509 eruptions are mainly driven by dykes. Magma mixing and interactions between resident
510 and intruding magmas are also recorded, but in this case they may be necessary for
511 opening a path towards the surface and allowing the magmas to erupt (Albert et al.,
512 2016). In this scenario, dykes that do not intercept previously emplaced magma pockets
513 may result in failed eruptions. Pdf volcano may be somewhere between these two end
514 members: intruding melts at depth are able to trigger eruptions by mobilizing shallower
515 isolated melt pockets, although they can also bypass them. This may be possible because
516 the shallow pockets may still be relatively well connected to the surface and can erupt.
517 Pdf may be an example of a high magma flux system, as Kilauea or Etna, but in which the
518 plumbing system connections between shallow pockets and deep conduits are not
519 necessarily active. More studies that contrast the depths and magmatic processes inferred
520 from monitoring networks with those obtained from crystals and host melt inclusions
521 should be able to clarify the different architecture of volcanic systems according to
522 magmatic fluxes and hopefully improve hazard mitigation strategies of associated
523 eruptions.

524

525 **7. Conclusions**

526 The olivine crystals and melt inclusions from the 2007 Pdf eruption record shallow
527 storage depth and re-equilibration related to lateral magma movement towards the
528 surface. Most crystals we have studied likely grew during the pre-eruption and eruption
529 period (e.g. in about 3 months) from the basalt that migrated from, and was temporarily

530 stored at shallow depths (e.g. about 0.5 km a.s.l), although deformation source modelled
531 from tilt data indicates an initially deeper magma source (ca. 3 km b.s.l.). These
532 observations suggest that magma arrival at shallow depth pressurized the pre-existing
533 melts and led to eruption of aphyric magma, but we have no evidence of physical
534 interaction between the two. The zoning and timescales derived from olivine crystals
535 agree with fast crystal growth, creation of a crystal mush and subsequent lateral
536 transport, eruption, and caldera collapse. Timescales deduced from Fe/Mg, Ni and Ca in
537 olivine rims and towards melt inclusions are relatively short (from 3 to 60 days) and agree
538 with the changes in monitoring data. P zoning in the crystal interiors also indicates
539 relatively short times (< 1.5 years) between olivine crystallization and eruption. Degassing
540 and re-equilibration of H⁺ of melt inclusions via diffusion occurred during the
541 depressurization of the shallow system and caldera collapse and vary between a few
542 hours to six days (depending on the crystallographic direction). Our results on the dynamic
543 of magmatic processes, vent locations, and magma transport have implications for similar
544 large mafic ocean island volcanoes such as Kilauea. However, the role of magma supply
545 rates that we propose to shape the plumbing systems of these volcanoes should be
546 further investigated by numerical or analogue experiments.

547

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725

726 **TABLE AND FIGURE CAPTIONS**

727 **Table 1.** Timescales (in days) calculated by modelling the chemical diffusion of Fe-Mg, Ni, Ca and P
728 in olivine crystals and at the interface with melt inclusions (MI).

729 **Table 2.** δD (‰), water content (wt %; error of $\pm 9\%$) and CO_2 (ppm; error of $\pm 10\%$). **Table 3.**
730 Timescales calculated from the H^+ diffusion in melt inclusions through the olivine crystals.

731 **Fig. 1. a)** Location of La Réunion Island. The red stars represent the February, March and April
732 2007 eruptive vents at Piton de la Fournaise. **b-h)** Back-scattered electron (BSE) images, forsterite
733 (Fo), and phosphorous (P) X-Ray compositional maps of representative olivine crystals from the
734 pre-caldera (b-d) and the post-caldera (e-h) samples. In the Fo maps, olivine crystals exhibit weak
735 reverse zoning from core to mantle (from Fo = 84 to Fo = 86) followed by a normal zoning towards
736 the rim (down to Fo = 82). Normal zoning (light blue colour in c, f and g) is also observed at the
737 interface between the olivine and the melt inclusions. These observations are common to both
738 samples. Black or white arrows show the location of the electron microprobe traverses and their
739 label; representative compositional profiles are shown in Fig. 2. Letters next to the melt inclusions
740 correspond to those reported in Tables 2 and 3. Panels d) and h) show the complex phosphorous
741 zoning of the olivine with “shadow” P-poor patterns surrounding some of the melt inclusions.

742 **Fig. 2.** Representative compositional profiles in olivine for Fo (mol %), CaO (wt %), NiO (wt %) and
743 P (mol%) measured from rim to core in olivine crystals (a, b) and around melt inclusions (d, e, f, g).
744 Timescales calculated using diffusion models are reported for each profile. Black lines are the best-
745 fit diffusion models computed using DIPRA (step-like and homogenous profile modelling for the
746 reverse and normal zoning respectively). Numbers in parentheses indicate the discrepancy of the
747 fit. **a)** Although the timescales for the three elements are similar, the large discrepancy obtained
748 for Ca suggest that these profiles are affected by crystal growth, thus the time may be
749 overestimated. **b)** Representative Fo and P profiles at the rim of the crystals. **c)** Conceptual
750 approach used for modelling the zoning patterns: step function for the reverse zoning in the
751 crystal core, and homogeneous profile and constant composition at the rim. **d)** Fe X-Ray
752 compositional map and two-dimensional diffusion model (white lines show increasing diffusion
753 times; see Supplementary Material Figure 2). Crystallographic axes directions are also shown. The
754 anisotropy effect is apparent, and the composition can be reproduced by a diffusion model (for 26
755 days). **e)** Fo and P profiles from traverses shown in d). Note that the one- and two-dimensional
756 models give very similar times. **f)** As in d), the anisotropic Fe zoning can be observed. **g)** P displays
757 a S-shaped profile and gives longer times that Fo probably due to significant contribution of
758 growth zoning.

759 **Fig. 3.** Frequency histogram displaying the distribution of the calculated timescales for different
760 elements (Fe-Mg, Ni, Ca and P) in olivine crystal rims and at the interface with melt inclusions.

761 **Fig. 4.** Volatile saturation pressures (H_2O-CO_2 ; Papale et al., 2006) calculated for olivine hosted
762 melt inclusions from eruptive products of the March 2007, pre- and post-caldera eruptions (April

763 2007). Olivine-melt equilibrium temperatures have been calculated using the Helz and Thornber
764 (1987) MgO geothermometer (error $\pm 10^\circ\text{C}$).

765 **Fig. 5.** Hydrogen-isotope fractionation (δD) versus dissolved water contents (relative error of $\pm 9\%$)
766 in the olivine hosted melt inclusions from the pre- (blue squares) and post-caldera (red squares)
767 phases of the April 2007 Piton de la Fournaise eruption. Solid curves are diffusion models
768 calculated from an initial composition of $\text{H}_2\text{O} = 1\text{-}1.3$ wt% and $\delta\text{D} = -100$ ‰ (yellow stars). The
769 diffusion models were computed with the following parameters: D calculated at 1160° parallel to
770 $[001]$, $k = 0.001$, $\beta = 0.3$ (Bucholz et al., 2013), $a = 50$ μm , $b = 500$ μm (a and b are average values from
771 Table 3). Diffusion parallel to $[100]$ and $[010]$ gives lower water contents. Dotted curves are the
772 degassing models for the same initial conditions (closed and open). Most pre-caldera samples
773 follow a general degassing trend, while post-caldera melt inclusions record variable degrees of H^+
774 diffusion.

775 **Fig. 6.** Correlation between the olivine and melt inclusions timescales with the geochemical and
776 geophysical data. The numbers above the first panel correspond to the numbers in the main text
777 (Section 5.3). **a)** The duration of the eruptions is represented by light grey bands. The onset of the
778 pre- and post- caldera eruptions is marked with a blue and a red line, respectively. The caldera
779 collapse event is represented with a dark grey band. **b)** Inflation-deflation cycle and correlation
780 with geological events. **c, d)** Timescales calculated from modelling the diffusion of Fe-Mg in the
781 pre- and post-caldera olivine crystals (error bars include NiO and CaO data when available) and of
782 H_2O in melt inclusions. Timescales are plotted from the eruption dates (3 and 25 April 2007), as
783 detailed in the main text (sections 4.3 and 4.4). The different timescales between crystals likely
784 reflect the range of transport times from the crystal-mush to the surface.

785 **Fig. 7.** Schematic model of the plumbing system processes preceding and during the 2007
786 eruption. For more details see main text (section 5.3).

787

788 **Table 1**

Sample-Crystal-MI	Traverse	Elem	P1	P2	B	α	β	γ	Time Core	Time Rim/MI*	$\Delta(-)$	$\Delta(+)$	Discr. (%)
<i>Crystal core-rim traverse</i>													
CM-2	1	Fo	85.3	86.0	83.6	50	84	45	413	47	48	53	7
CM-2	1	Ni	0.28	0.31	0.21	50	84	45	413	48	55	62	12
CM-2	1	Ca	0.272	0.240	0.295	50	84	45	413	77	49	55	20
CM-2	2	Fo	84.1	85.7	82.8	35	84	55	764	14	81	92	16
CM-2	2	Ni	0.25	0.31	0.26	35	84	55	764	3	88	103	10
CM-2	2	Ca	0.275	0.240	0.326	35	84	55	764	30	84	96	24
CM-3	1	Fo		85.6	83.6	85	15	76	-	45	9	7	14
CM-3	1	Ni		0.29	0.23	85	15	76	-	23	18	8	13
CM-3	1	Ca		0.256	0.308	85	15	76	-	32	17	19	11
CM-3	2	Fo	83.9	85.2	84.2	85	25	65	833	31	90	103	16
CM-3	2	Ni	0.24	0.30	0.25	85	25	65	833	62	131	120	14
CM-3	2	Ca	0.292	0.250	-	85	25	65	833	157	194	180	20
CM-6	1	Fo		85.6	84.3	85	25	65	-	58	10	11	6
CM-6	1	Ni		0.29	0.23	85	25	65	-	23	3	8	9
CM-6	1	Ca		0.250	0.305	85	25	65	-	49	14	17	15
CM-6	2	Fo		85.70	84.53	86	75	15	-	64	9	11	14
CM-6	2	Ni		0.29	0.21	86	75	15	-	47	8	14	8
CM-6	2	Ca		0.250	0.295	86	75	15	-	56	10	13	5
251-17	4	Fo		84.9	82.1	87	3	89	-	37	6	10	<1
251-17	5	Fo		84.8	82.9	86	9	83	-	16	2	5	<1
251-20	3	Fo		84.5	83.5	46	52	67	-	16	5	3	4
251-22	1	Fo		84.6	82.4	3	90	88	-	29	3	6	2
251-25	2	Fo		84.5	81.5	84	43	47	-	9	2	3	1
CM-2-MI-a	6	Fo	84.1		82.4	80	84	11	-	18	3	5	4
CM-3-MI-a	7	Fo	84.2		83.0	85	15	76	-	30	4	22	3
CM-3-MI-a	8	Fo	84.2		82.8	86	75	15	-	23	6	8	1
251-17-MI-a	5	Fo	84.7		83.4	87	35	55	-	2	1	1	2
251-20-MI-a	3	Fo	84.2		83.2	46	52	67	-	7	2	2	1
251-25-MI-a	3	Fo	84.5		83.3	78	83	14	-	8	3	3	<1
251-25-MI-a	3	P	4.9E-3		6.4E-5	78	83	14	-	560	78	77	2
251-25-MI-a	4	Fo	84.5		83.5	89	5	85	-	15	3	10	<1

P1 and P2 are the two compositional plateaus observed leading to reverse zoning. B is the

boundary composition. We report the angles between the traverses and the three crystallographic axis (α , β , γ) and the discrepancy value (in percentage). The analytical errors are ± 0.2 for the Fo (mol%), ± 0.02 for the NiO (wt%), ± 0.008 for the CaO (wt%), and ± 0.001 for the P (mol%). *Timescales have been calculated considering a homogeneous profile and constant composition; a step-like modelling would give times about 50% shorter. Sample nomenclature is as follows: 1) CM- and 251- refer to the pre- and post-caldera samples; 2) numbers after the hyphen refer to the crystal, and 3) melt inclusions have been designated with letters (e.g. CM-2-a is the melt inclusion a in the olivine 2 of the sample CM). The temperatures and fO₂ values for the modelling were chosen according to the values calculated from the olivine MIs. Both correspond to the averages for the two populations of MIs.

789 **Table 2**

Sample-Crystal	M I	Pre-caldera samples						Post-caldera samples								
		δD	δD error	H ₂ O	CO ₂	P	Depth	Crystal	MI	δD	δD error	H ₂ O	CO ₂	P	Depth	
CM-2	a			0.93	94	336	1683	251-4	a			0.64				
CM-2	b			0.72				251-6	a			0.71				
CM-3	a	-39.2	7.3	0.87	104	330	1653	251-8	a			0.38				
CM-4	a	-10.3	6.8	0.84				251-11	a			0.45				
CM-4	b	-46.9	5.1	0.79	86	285	1427	251-14	a			0.38				
CM-4	c			0.67				251-15	a	-51	7	0.8	75	228	1137	
CM-5	b			0.86				251-16	a	-7	5.8	0.75	79	187	927	
CM-17	a			0.75				251-16	b	-22	6.4	0.79	89	244	1219	
CM-17	b			0.61				251-17	a	11	6.5	0.72				
CM-27	a			0.81				251-17	d	62	8	0.6				
CM-29	a			0.77				251-19	a	-63	6	0.79	133	250	1249	
CM-29	b			0.79				251-20	a	-23	6.5	0.7				
CM-30	a			0.92				251-20	b	-77	6	0.68	114	228	1137	
CM-30	b			0.69				251-22	a	-36	6	0.74	75	211	1050	
CM-35	a	-115	5	0.71	94	232	1158	251-22	c	22	7	0.77				
CM-36	a	-85	6	0.96	104	256	1280	251-22	h	-51	7	0.82	74	216	1076	
CM-36	b	-102	4	0.77				251-24	b			0.32	56	106	506	

CM-39	a	-110	4	113				251-24	c	-11	7.1	0.66	60	166	818
CM-39	b	-135	5	1.09	101	313	1567	251-25	a	-30	6.3	0.67	204	367	1837
CM-40	a	-104	4	0.95	111	327	1638								
CM-40	b				95										
CM-43	a	-119	7	0.85	53	173	855								
CM-44	a	-103	6	0.93	76	250	1249								
CM-45	a	-108	4	0.89	99	286	1432								
CM-46	c			0.8	124	339	1697								

H₂O, CO₂, saturations pressures and depth data from Di Muro et al., (2014). Saturation pressure (P) in bars and calculated corresponding depth below the crater in meters. Major element composition, diameter and the presence or not of a vapor bubble for each melt inclusion can be found in the supplementary material.

790 **Table 3**

Sample-Crystal	MI	<i>a</i> (μm)	<i>b</i> (μm)	α	ϕ (%)	Time in days	
						D=1.6x10 ⁻¹¹ m ² /s	D=1.2x10 ⁻¹² m ² /s
						([001])	([100], [010])
CM-3	a	63	438	0.144	19-43	0.1-0.4 (6.3)	2.2-5.4 (85)
CM-2	a	50	543	0.092	10-37	0.1-0.2 (4.3)	1.1-3.3 (57)
251-17	a	53	467	0.114	39-57	0.3-0.4 (4.7)	3.6-6.0 (63)
251-17	d	40	600	0.067	57-70	0.3-0.4 (2.8)	3.9-5.4 (38)
251-20	a	130	520	0.250	43-60	1.4-2.3 (23)	19-32 (314)
251-20	b	41	353	0.116	44-61	0.2-0.3 (2.8)	2.5-3.9 (37)
251-22	a	54	462	0.116	37-56	0.2-0.4 (4.8)	3.5-5.9 (64)
251-25	a	45	550	0.082	47-63	0.3-0.4 (3.5)	3.6-5.4 (47)

a is the radius of the melt inclusions and *b* is the shortest distance to the crystal rim measured in the BSE images. α is the ratio between *a* and *b*. For the calculation of the re-equilibration degree

(ϕ) of melt inclusions we have considered as initial range of dissolved water 1-1.3 H₂O wt % and a final equilibrium concentration of 0.3 wt % in agreement with Di Muro et al. (2014). We provide the times calculated for D parallel to [001], [100] and [010] axes at 1160°C. The two timescales depend on the initial composition, and hence on the re-equilibration degree. The values in parenthesis are the time required to achieve a $\phi = 100\%$. In addition to the inherent uncertainties of Qin et al. (1992) model, these calculations are assuming a constant H⁺ composition at the crystal boundary during magma ascent and neglecting the tridimensional geometry of the crystals and melt inclusions.